

ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF FOOD GRAIN WAREHOUSES IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The efficient management and storage of food grains play a pivotal role in ensuring food security in India, particularly in Maharashtra, one of the country's key agricultural states. This study rigorously assesses existing warehousing infrastructure and facilities provided by the Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation (MSWC) in Nagpur District, focusing on data collected from 45 farmers of three tehsils of Nagpur District for the year 2023-24. The findings that The Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation offers farmers affordable storage solutions by reducing storage charges by 50% discount on storage charges and 25 % space has been reserved in godowns for agricultural produce and storage of agricultural produce is given priority. However, despite this support, a survey of selected farmers revealed that while all were aware of basic warehousing functions, and partially aware about knowledge of the warehouse receipt system, and just few farmers knew about the regulatory authority overseeing warehousing, indicating a lack of awareness about crucial aspects. The study also identified key constraints faced by farmers, such as the distance from warehouses as a major issues, lack of awareness of government subsidies, maintenance facilities, transportation, and storage damages. Only few farmers considered high storage costs a concern, suggesting that informational and logistical challenges overshadow financial barriers. For warehouse stakeholders, the Garrett ranking technique highlighted insufficient stock receipts, rejection of low-quality goods, and low payments from government entities as the main issues for investors, while warehouse managers emphasized labor shortages and responsibility for storage losses. These findings underscore the need for better education, outreach, and addressing logistical and operational challenges to enhance warehousing efficiency in Nagpur

Keywords: MSWC; Food Grain Warehouses; Warehouse receipt system; awareness; willingness to participate; garret ranking technique; storage.

Introduction and Objective

Food grain warehouses are essential components of the agricultural supply chain, playing a pivotal role in ensuring food security and market stability. Historically, grain storage in India was managed through traditional methods such as earthen silos, wooden bins, and metal containers, which were largely decentralized and small in scale. However, with the Green Revolution in the 1960s and the subsequent increase in grain production, the need for modern and large-scale storage facilities became evident. This led to the establishment of more structured grain warehousing systems, managed by both government and private entities. The government of India, through agencies like the Food Corporation of India (FCI), Central Warehousing Corporation (CWC), and State Warehousing Corporations (SWCs), has been instrumental in developing and maintaining grain warehouses across the country. These agencies ensure that there is sufficient storage capacity to handle the seasonal surges in grain production and to maintain buffer stocks for public distribution and emergency situations.

Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation (MSWC) was established on 8th August, 1957, under the Agriculture Produce (Development & Warehousing) Act, 1956, which was subsequently replaced by the Warehousing Corporations Act, 1962. MSWC is one of the oldest State Warehousing Corporation in the country. It was started with 3 Warehousing Centers and has now grown up to the extent of 205 Centers as at present with a total capacity of 18.59 Lakhs MTs (as on 15th Oct. 2023)

In Maharashtra, 8 divisional offices (Amravati, Kolhapur, Nagpur, Pune, Latur, Mumbai, Nashik and Aurangabad) and network of warehouse centers at 205 locations and 1204 godowns, total storage capacity 20.85 lakhs tons. among them in Nagpur division, 19 main center of Maharashtra state warehousing corporation, among them 4 main centers included in Nagpur district their are Butibori, Saoner, Katol and Wadi Hingana. which manage, regulate also providing warehousing facilities under Maharashtra state warehouse corporation in Nagpur district.

This research paper aims to evaluate existing Food Grain warehouses in Nagpur district, focusing on the awareness level about warehousing facilities among the farmers and constraints faced by farmers in adopting and utilizing the Food Grain warehouses. and Garrett's ranking technique, this study will analyze the key issues reported by

stakeholders. The findings will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of warehousing system and utilization of warehousing facilities and suggest actionable recommendations for enhancing its performance.

The specific objectives of the study are:

To examine existing food Grain-warehouses in Nagpur district with respect to capacity and facilities.

To study the awareness level among the farmers regarding the food Grain warehouse facilities and their utilization pattern.

To analyse the constraints faced by stakeholders for food Grain warehousing facilities.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in Nagpur district, focusing on three tahsils: Saoner, Katol, and Hingana. These tahsils were purposively selected due to the presence of key centers of the Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation in the area. A total of 45 farmers participated in the study, with 15 farmers chosen from each tahsil. Specifically, five farmers were selected from each of three villages within Saoner, Katol, and Hingana, ensuring a representative sample from all three regions. This approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the farmers' experiences with warehousing facilities across the selected tahsils. The primary data were collected personally with the help of interview schedules; the interviews were conducted in farmer's fields or in their homes through face-to-face contact.

To accomplish the objectives of the present study simple tabular analysis was used along with the frequency, percentage, graphical representation, etc.

Garret Ranking technique

To analyse the constraints faced by stakeholders in the warehousing sector, the Garrett ranking technique was employed. This method helps prioritize various challenges by ranking them in descending order of importance based on the perceptions of the stakeholders. Each constraint was assigned a rank according to its severity and impact on the stakeholders.

Results and Discussion

To examine existing food grain warehouses in Nagpur District with respect to capacity and facilities.

Main centres of Food Grain Warehouses under MSWC with their storage capacity (M.T) in Nagpur District

The main centers of Food Grain Warehouses under MSWC with their storage capacity were presented in Table No.1 indicate that significant storage capacity of the four main centers of the Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation (MSWC) in Nagpur district, which collectively offer a total capacity of 41,858 metric tons (M.T). Additionally, the table shows that 11,084 M.T of this capacity remains vacant, indicating available storage space within the district's warehousing infrastructure. This data underscores the efficient utilization of these centers while also emphasizing the potential for accommodating additional goods.

Rental rates for storage in food grain warehouses as per schedule of MSWC

The Rental rates for storage in food grain warehouses as per schedule of MSWC were presented in Table No.2 indicate that basic storage rate per bag per month (Rs.) for farmers under MSWC in Nagpur District. By offering a 50% discount on storage charges, MSWC significantly reduces the financial burden on farmers, making storage more affordable. Additionally, reserving 25% of warehouse space specifically for agricultural produce ensures that a substantial portion of storage capacity is dedicated to farmers' needs. These measures, combined with prioritizing the storage of agricultural produce, demonstrate MSWC's commitment to facilitating efficient warehousing solutions and supporting the agricultural sector. These initiatives are expected to improve the overall storage infrastructure and address some of the key challenges faced by farmers.

To study the awareness level among the farmers regarding the food grain warehouse facilities and their utilization pattern.

To study awareness level among farmers regarding the Food Grain Warehousing System

To study the awareness level among farmers regarding food grain warehouse facilities and their utilization patterns, primary data were collected from selected farmers through personal interviews using interview schedule, which included a set of 10 carefully designed questions aimed at assessing the respondents' knowledge and utilization of warehousing facilities are detailed in Table No.3 reveals a varied level of awareness among the 45 selected farmers regarding the warehousing system. While all respondents (100%) were aware about basic information of warehouses, only respondents (48.88%) have knowledge of the warehouse receipt system, indicating partial awareness of its functionality. Moreover, only respondents (4.44%)

Table No. 1 Main centres of Food Grain Warehouses under MSWC with their storage capacity (M.T) in Nagpur District

Sr. No.	Main centre name with code	Total capacity (M.T.)	Vacant space (M.T.)
1.	Butibori (1315)	4263	0
2.	Katol (1316)	5200	4115
3.	Saoner (1337)	5930	5782
4.	Wadi Hingana (1317)	26465	1187
Total		41,858	11,084

Table No. 2 Rental rates for storage in food grain godown as per schedule of MSWC

Quantity of food grain	Numbers of storage bags (quintal)	Basic storage rate per bag per month (Rs.)			
		A grade	B grade	C+ grade	C grade
51 to 100 kgs and more than	> 100	9.90	9.60	9.30	9.10
	51 to 100	10.40	10.10	9.80	9.40
	1 to 50	10.60	10.40	10.10	9.90

Table No. 3 To study awareness level among farmers regarding the Food Grain Warehousing System

Sr No	Statements	Frequency	Percentage to total
1.	Do you know about warehouse	45	100
2.	Do you know any public warehouse	28	62.22
3.	Do you know any food grain warehouse	32	71.11
4.	Is there any warehouse nearby your village	25	55.55
5.	Do you know about warehouse receipt system	22	48.88

was aware of the authority that regulates the warehousing sector, highlighting a significant gap in knowledge regarding regulatory aspects. This data suggests that while farmers have a basic understanding of warehouse systems, their awareness of more advanced aspects like the receipt system and regulatory bodies is limited, indicating the need for better education and outreach to improve their understanding of these essential components of the warehousing system

Constraints faced by selected farmers regarding Food Grain Warehousing facilities

Constraints faced by selected farmers regarding Food Grain Warehouses are presented in Table No. 4 indicate that key constraints faced by farmers in utilizing warehouse facilities. The majority of farmers (15.57%) identified the primary issue as the distance of warehouses from their fields, making access difficult. This was followed by 13.33% of farmers who reported a lack of awareness about government subsidies available for warehousing. Additionally, 5% of farmers faced issues related to lack of proper guidelines for facility maintenance, damage during storage, and inadequate transportation facilities, respectively. Only 4.44% of farmers cited high storage charges as a significant concern. These findings suggest that logistical and informational barriers, rather than cost, are the predominant challenges farmers encounter with warehousing facilities.

Constraints faced by the stakeholders in warehousing system

Constraints faced by Stakeholders regarding Food Grain Warehousing system presented in Table No. 5 analyzed using the Garrett ranking technique, reveals the key problems faced by warehouse stakeholders, For warehouse investors, the most significant issue is the insufficient receipt of stock for storage, which was ranked highest in terms of importance. This is followed by rejection of stocks due to poor quality, and the low payments from government entities for storing commodities, which ranked third. Additionally, the unavailability of labor for loading, unloading, and stocking also emerged as a notable concern. On the other hand, warehouse managers identified the unavailability of labor for handling arrivals as the major problem, with responsibility for unjustified losses during storage ranking second. These findings underscore the critical challenges in warehousing, highlighting both logistical and financial constraints that need to be addressed to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of warehouse operations.

6.	Is every warehouse provide WRS	20	44.44
7.	Do you know bank provide loan against WRS	15	33.33
8.	Do you know the procedure of loan against WRS	5	11.11
9.	Do you listen about electronic warehouse receipt system	3	6.66
10.	Do you know which authority regulate warehousing sector	2	4.44

Table No. 4 Constraints faced by selected farmers regarding Food Grain Warehousing facilities

Sr. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Percentage to total
1.	High storage charge	2	4.44
2.	Reluctant due to small quantity for storage	4	8.89
3.	Delay in getting storage space	2	4.44
4.	Large distance from field	7	15.57
5.	Lack of transportation facility	5	11.11
6.	lack of awareness about government subsidies	6	13.33
7.	Lack of proper guide lines regarding storing	4	8.89
8.	Inadequate storage space	2	4.44
9.	Lack of proper guide lines regarding maintaining of warehouse	5	11.11
10.	Damage due to storage	5	11.11
11.	Immediate need of cash	3	6.67
Total		45	100

Table No. 5 Constraints faced by the stakeholders in warehousing system

Sr. No.	Constraints	Garret's mean score	Rank
1.	Less arrivals of stock for storage in godown	69.37	I
2.	Rejection of stocks due to poor quality leads to less quantity of storage in godown	62.5	II
3.	Low payments from government entities for storing commodities	41.25	III
4.	Unavailability of labour for loading, unloading and stocking	33.75	IV

Conclusion

The analysis of the storage capacity and utilization of the Maharashtra State Warehousing Corporation (MSWC) centers in Nagpur district reveals both strengths and areas for improvement. The four main centers collectively provide 41,858 metric tons (M.T) of capacity, with 11,084 M.T remaining vacant, indicating the potential to accommodate additional goods and optimize warehouse usage. The MSWC's 50% discount on storage charges significantly reduces the financial burden on farmers, and reserving 25% of space for agricultural produce ensures farmers have dedicated storage options. However, the study highlights gaps in farmers' awareness, with only partial understanding of advanced systems like the warehouse receipt system and regulatory authorities. This suggests the need for enhanced education and outreach to improve farmers' knowledge of these essential components. and the Key constraints faced by farmers include logistical challenges, such as the distance of warehouses from their fields and lack of awareness about government subsidies, while financial barriers like high storage charges were of lesser concern. Similarly, warehouse stakeholders, including investors and managers, face critical challenges, such as insufficient stock receipt, rejection of low-quality goods, and labor shortages for handling arrivals. These logistical, financial, and operational issues underscore the need for targeted interventions to enhance both farmer engagement and warehouse efficiency. Addressing these challenges will be essential for improving the overall effectiveness of warehousing operations in the district.

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